

Influence of Gender Based Violence on Students 'Academic Achievements in Public Senior Secondary Schools of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa State

Ifeoma Grace Oriaku, Eunice Ijeoma Ezugwu and Theresa Folashade Kolade

Department of Educational Foundations

Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria.

Received 5 February 2025; Acceptance 9 March 2025; Published 18 March 2025.

Abstract

The study examined the influence of gender based violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa State. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised of 22,330 SS2 students in 96 public senior secondary schools in 5 local government areas of Nasarawa West senatorial Zone. Three hundred and eighty four (384) students were selected for the study using Research Advisors Table (2006). The researcher developed a 10-item instrument named Questionnaire on Gender Based Violence (QOGEBAV) for the purpose of data collection. In addition, a 40-item English Language Achievement Test (ELAT) of multiple choice format was adapted. The instruments were subjected to validation by experts in Educational Psychology and Measurement and Evaluation in order to ascertain their face and content validity. In the process, the researcher established a logical validity index of the 0.84 and 0.82 respectively for the questionnaire and English language achievement test. The instruments were further subjected to pilot study with data obtained was computed using Cronbach Alpha statistics. Results obtained from the yielded reliability indices of 0.75 and 0.76 respectively. The research questions were answered using frequency count and simple percentage while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level using chi-square statistics. The findings from the study showed there is a significant influence of physical violence on students' academic achievement of public senior secondary schools of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa State, and there is a significant influence of emotional violence on students' academic achievement of public senior secondary schools of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa State, The study recommended that awareness campaigns should be

Correspondence to: Ifeoma Grace Oriaku, e-mail: ifeomaoriaku4@gmail.com

Copyright: © 2025 The authors. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

How to Cite: Oriaku et al. (2025). Influence of Gender Based Violence on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa State, *Scholar J - Science and Education*, 3(3). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15045873

organized through events and social media platforms in communities for the purpose of curbing gender based domestic so that students achievement may be enhanced in schools.

Keywords: Gender Based Violence, Students Academic Achievement, Physical Violence, Emotional Violence.

Introduction

Education is regarded as an asset both in developing and developed countries of the world. Education enables individuals, groups, countries and human race to explore, appreciate, understand and develop their physical and social environments for the satisfaction of their needs. It empowers individuals and liberates citizens from ignorance, prejudice, bias, superstition, and manipulation by people who claim to have superior knowledge (Okeye, 2019). Education, no doubt, is the key to national development, thus, it is intended to serve the expressed goals and aspirations of the country as enshrined in the National Policy on Education. The role that education is expected to play in a society is multifaceted. It is expected to build the character of the learner, to get him informed about what is worthwhile, acceptable to society, desirable and purposeful for himself, his environment and society (Ayeni and Aderinkola, 2023)). The invaluable roles and contributions of education in the development of an individual and the society cannot be over emphasized. It is however important to note that for education to yield meaningful learning outcomes in terms of students' academic achievement, the physical and emotional state of the learner is paramount. This is because quality education is intended to bring about improved academic achievement in school. Duke (2015) noted that the level of academic achievement of students is primarily determined by the level of achievement in courses and programs. One common trend that runs through all the definitions of academic achievement presented above is that academic achievement is linked to achievement of knowledge and excellence. Fajemidagba and Sule. (2019) further sees academic achievement as the output of students' evaluation in the educational process indicating to what level the students have achieved in the educational goal as specified in the school curriculum, which greatly influenced by internal and external classroom factors. It is a cumulative function of current and prior scores. Hence, the academic achievement of students in Nasarawa West Senatorial District has not been encouraging. WAEC Nov//Dec results between 2022 and 2024 showed that 42.16%, passed in 2022 44.29% passed in 2023 and 53.64% passed in 2024. It is observed that passes in 2022 and 2023 were below 50 percent. This poor trend therefore calls for concern.

Supol et al. (2021) identified violence as one of the key factors responsible for poor academic achievement

Domestic violence, a significant global issue, has profound effects on various aspects of individuals' lives, particularly secondary school student. The impact of domestic violence on student's academic achievement cannot be overemphasized, as it influences not only immediate educational outcomes but also long-term development and well-being. Domestic violence is a pervasive social issue that transcends cultural, economic, and geographical boundaries, affecting millions of individuals worldwide. In Nigeria, domestic violence remains a significant concern, with far-reaching consequences not only for the direct victims but also for students who witness or experience violence within the home (Daramola, 2025). These students, who are often considered the silent victims of domestic violence, face a myriad of challenges that extend beyond the immediate physical or emotional trauma (Ikechukwu & Adeyemi, 2020). Domestic violence refers to a pattern of abusive behaviors used by one partner in a marriage, dating, family, or cohabitation relationship to keep control over another intimate partner. In order to influence someone else, one can use various forms of violence such as physical and emotional violence. (Ikechukwu & Adeyemi, 2020).

Physical violence is any intentional act causing injury or trauma to another person or animal by way of bodily contact. In most cases, children are the victims of physical abuse, but adults can also be victims, as in cases of domestic violence or workplace aggression. Alternative terms sometimes used include physical assault. Physical violence is often defined as the use of physical force or power by humans to cause harm and degradation to other living beings, such as humiliation, pain, injury, disablement, damage to property and ultimately death, as well as destruction to a society's living environment. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2025) defines physical violence as "the intentional use of physical force or power, threatened or actual, against oneself, another person, or against a group or community, which either results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injury, death, psychological harm, maldevelopment, or deprivation." There is growing recognition among researchers and practitioners of the need to include violence that does not necessarily result in injury or death (Alabi and Oni, 2017; Daramola, 2025).

Emotional violence on the other hand includes restricting a child's movements, denigration, ridicule, threats and intimidation, discrimination, rejection and other non-physical forms of hostile treatment. Emotional violence is a form of abuse characterized by a person subjecting or exposing another person to a behavior that may result in psychological trauma, including anxiety, chronic depression, clinical depression or post-traumatic stress disorder amongst other psychological problems (Mtasingwa and Mwaipopo, 2022). It is often associated with situations of power imbalance in abusive relationships, and may include bullying, gaslighting, abuse in the workplace, amongst other behaviors that may cause an individual to feel unsafe. It also may be perpetrated by persons conducting torture,

other violence, acute or prolonged human rights abuse, particularly without legal redress such as detention without trial, false accusations, false convictions, and extreme defamation such as where perpetrated by state and media.

Different studies exist in the literature on gender-based violence. Mokolapo and Oloruntola (2022) investigated the influence of physical domestic violence on the academic performance of secondary school students in Ado-Ekiti, the capital city of Ekiti State. The study revealed that there is significant influence of domestic violence on the academic performance of secondary school students. The study also revealed the impact of exposure to domestic violence irrespective of their gender on the attitudinal behavioural pattern of secondary school students, showing that students who got exposed to domestic violence tend to exhibit or involve in violent activities within the school or in the community. In like vein, Alabi and Oni (2017) examined the impact of emotional, physical, economic and psychological and violence on child academic performance in Owo Local Government Area. Finding show that prevalence of all forms of domestic violence such as physical, economic, emotional and psychological in most of the homes investigated and had significant impact on child academic performance irrespective of gender.

Moreover, the purpose of learning in any school environment is to ensure a permanent change in behaviour. This however, can only be achieved if all hands are on deck to ensure that the school and home environment becomes a safe haven for effective teaching and learning. It is based on this realization that the present study is geared towards examining the influence of gender-based violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the influence of physical violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa?
2. What is the influence of emotional violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided this study and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant influence of physical violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa.
2. There is no significant influence of emotional violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa.

Research Method

Descriptive survey research design was used in this study. The population of the study comprises 22,330 SS2 students in 96 public senior secondary schools in 5 local government areas of Nasarawa West senatorial Zone. Three hundred and eighty four (384) students were selected using Research Advisors Table (2006). The instrument used for data collection was a structured 10-item questionnaire named Questionnaire on Gender Based Violence (QOGEBAV). In addition, a 40-item English Language Achievement Test (ELAT) was developed for the study for the purpose assessing students' academic achievement in English Language. The two instruments were subjected to the scrutiny of experts in Economics and Evaluation this provided scores that were used to obtain logical validity indices of 0.84 and 0.82 respectively. The instruments were further subjected to pilot study. The instruments were pilot tested on 30 students; the respondents were part of the population but not part of the sample for this study. Even though the instruments were standardized, they were still subjected to reliability in order to ascertain their degree of consistency. The data obtained from the pilot test was used to compute the internal consistency of the instrument using Cronbach's Alpha reliability method. Results obtained from the exercise were used to obtain reliability indices of 0.75 and 0.76 for the questionnaire and achievement tests in economics respectively. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions developed for the study while t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Questions 1: What is influence of physical violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa.

Table 1. Mean and Standard Showing influence of physical violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa

Items	Gender	N	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std Dev	Remarks
	Male	211	43	112	42	14	2.87	0.81	Agreed
1. I often get slapped and this makes me unable to concentrate and learn better in school	Female	173	41	108	12	12	3.04	1.17	Agreed
	Male	211	113	28	35	35	3.04	0.78	Agreed
2. I get kicked by other children and this makes me unable to learn better	Female	173	45	53	75	0	2.94	0.97	
	Male	211	71	77	42	21	3.06	0.79	Agreed
3. I have suffered from injuries and wounds that are too painful for me to endure and stay focused on my studies.	Female	173	40	58	23	52	2.53	1.12	
	Male	211	56	49	57	49	3.08	0.79	Agreed
4. My friends and I often get pushed by stronger children and this explains									

why I am unable to learn better in school.	Female	173	57	104	12	0	3.19	0.75	Agreed
	Male	211	77	35	57	42	2.87	0.81	Agreed
5. My personal belongings are sometimes forcefully taken from me by other students in school	Female	173	56	46	71	0	3.04	1.17	Agreed
	Male								
Average mean	Male						2.97	0.79	
	Female						2.88	1.03	

Table 1 shows the influence of physical violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa. Results indicate that most of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed to the items on the questionnaire. The cluster mean values of male and female respondents is given as 2.97 and 2.88. these values are above the benchmark value of 2.50 for a four point scaled questionnaire. Hence, physical violence has a high influence violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa.

Research Questions 2: What is influence of emotional violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa.

Table 2. Mean and Standard Showing influence of emotional violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa.

Items	Gender	N	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std Dev	Remarks
	Male	211	56	49	57	49	2.87	0.81	Agreed
6. Threats from other learners makes me uneasy to learn	Female	173	57	104	12	0	3.04	1.17	Agreed
	Male	211	113	28	35	35	3.04	0.78	Agreed
7. Being insulted makes me feel unhappy to learn and perform better in school .	Female	173	45	53	75	0	2.94	0.97	
	Male	211	77	35	57	71	3.06	0.79	Agreed
8. I often get blamed by others and this makes me too upset to concentrate on my studies.	Female	173	56	46	71	0	2.53	1.12	
	Male	211	56	49	57	49	2.87	0.81	Agreed
9. The feeling of being ignored by others around me has discouraged me from learning better in school ..	Female	173	57	104	12	0	3.04	1.17	Agreed

	Male	211	77	35	57	42	2.81	0.80	Agreed
10. Hearing statements that makes me feel inferior distracts me from concentrating on my studies.	Female	173	56	46	71	0	2.70	1.16	Agreed
Cluster mean	Male						2.93	0.80	
	Female						2.88	1.03	

Table 2 shows the influence of emotional violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa. Results indicate that most of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed to the items on the questionnaire. The cluster mean values of male and female respondents is given as 2.93 and 2.88. these values are above the benchmark value of 2.50 for a four point scaled questionnaire. Hence, emotional violence has a high influence violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant influence of physical violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa.

Table 3. t-test Statistics showing the influence of physical violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa.

Gender	N	Mean Response	Std Dev	Mean Achievement	Std Dev	t-cal	Sig	Remarks
Male	211	2.97	0.79	63.00	7.94	23.00	0.012	Significant
Female	173	2.88	1.03	51.12	7.15			

Table 3 above shows the t-test statistics on the influence of physical violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa.. The results showed that at X^2 calculated value of 23.00, the p-value of 0.012 was found to be less than 0.05. Hence, the result reveals that there is a significant influence of physical violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender .

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant effect of influence of emotional violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender

Table 4. t-test Statistics showing the influence of emotional violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa.

Gender	N	Mean Response	Std Dev	Mean Achievement	Std Dev	t-cal	Sig	Remarks
Male	211	2.93	0.80	65.00	8.06	18.34	0.012	Significant
Female	173	2.88	1.03	50.18	7.08			

Table 4 above shows the t-test statistics on the influence of emotional violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender of Nasarawa West Senatorial District of Nasarawa. The results showed that at X^2 calculated value of 18.34, the p-value of 0.012 was found to be less than 0.05. Hence, the result reveals that there is a significant influence of emotional violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender.

Discussion

Findings from the study on hypothesis one reveal there is a significant effect of virtual learning integration technology on the learning interest of public senior secondary school students in public senior secondary school of the FCT, Abuja. This finding is in agreement with the findings from the study of Salihu (2021) which indicated there was a significant effect of virtual reality-based instruction on students' interest and conceptual Performance in Senior Secondary School Physics. This entails that employing virtual learning integration technology enhances students' learning interest.

Findings from the study on hypothesis two reveal there is a significant effect of virtual learning integration technology on the academic achievement in public senior secondary schools of the FCT, Abuja. This

finding is in agreement with the findings from the study of Ayeni and Aderinkola (2023) which there was significant effect of virtual learning on students' academic performance in mathematics. This entails that employing virtual learning technology in the course of instructional delivery helps in improving students' academic achievement.

Conclusion

The study concludes that there is significant influence of physical violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender. Findings further reveal that there is significant influence of emotional violence on students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools when segregated according to gender. Based on these results, it was therefore recommended among others that schools should be equipped by the Federal ministry of Education with virtual learning tools for the purpose of creating an enabling environment that will enhance students' learning interest. Additionally, periodic trainings and seminars should be organized by the Federal Ministry of Education for teachers in order to facilitate the effective use of virtual learning technological devices that may enhance students' academic achievement.

References

- Alabi, O.T. and Oni, I.O. (2017). Impact of domestic violence on the academic performance of secondary school students in Owo local Government, Nigeria. *Afro Asian Journal of Social Sciences*, Volume VIII, No II. Quarter II 2017.
- Ayeni, A. & Aderinkola, D. (2023). Effect of Virtual Learning on Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics in Post Covid-19 Era. *AJSTME*, Vol. 8, Special Issue No. 1, 456-462.
- Daramola, C.O. (2025). Domestic Violence and Its Effects on Academics Performance of Secondary School Students in Ikere- Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria. *British Journal of Multidisciplinary and Advanced Studies*, 6(1),87-112, 2025.
- Duke, N. (2015) For the rich its richer, print environments and experience offered to first grade students in very low and high – SES school Zone s *American Educational Research Journal*, 37 (7), 456 – 457.
- Fajemidagba, P.L., Sule, K. (2019). Determinants of Individuals' Differences and Gender Differences in Knowledge. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 93 (4), 787-825.
- Ikechukwu, A., & Adeyemi, S. (2020). Domestic violence and its impact on child development in Nigeria. *Journal of Nigerian Studies*, 15(3), 45-60.
- Mokolapo, T. O and Oloruntola, B.A (2022) investigated the influence of domestic violence on the academic performance of secondary school students in Ado–Ekiti, the capital city of Ekiti State. *African Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research ISSN: 2689-5129 Volume 5, Issue 5, 2022.*
- Mtasingwa, L.V & Mwaipopo, R (2022) investigated Gender-based Violence and its Impact to Secondary School Students' Education Participation, Retention and Performance in Bagamoyo and Chalinze districts, Coastal region, Tanzania. *Tanzania Journal of Development Studies*, Vol. 20, No. 1, 2022: 62–86.

Okeye, J. (2019) Effects of public and private schools on academic achievement. *Seoul Journal of Economics*, 27, 137 – 147

Research Advisors (2006). *Sample Size Table*. <https://research-advisors.com/tools/SampleSize.htm>

Saliyu, A. (2021). Effect of virtual reality based instruction on students' interest and conceptual performance of physics in dutsin-ma zonal education quality assurance, katsina state nigeria. 10.13140/rg.2.2.29148.05764.

Supol, M., Satyen, L., Minaie, M. G. & Toumbourou, J. (2020). Effects of Family Violence Exposure on Adolescent Academic Achievement: A Systematic Review. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*. 22. 152483801989948. 10.1177/1524838019899486.

World Health Organization (2025). The VPA Approach. <https://www.who.int/groups/violence-prevention-alliance/approach>

Publisher's Note Scholar J remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.